

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE REVISED K-12 CURRICULUM AND THE LEARNERS' READING PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum and its relationship to learners' reading performance in the districts of Calape and Tubigon West. It employed a descriptive–correlational research design, gathering data from teachers to assess curriculum implementation in terms of curriculum content and design, teaching and learning enhancement, and implementation support. Findings revealed that teachers generally had positive perceptions of the curriculum, particularly in its alignment with national standards, clarity of objectives, and promotion of learner-centered and flexible teaching approaches. In terms of reading performance, most learners demonstrated high proficiency levels, although some still required targeted interventions. Statistical analysis showed no significant differences in curriculum implementation when grouped according to grade level, teaching experience, and number of trainings attended, indicating consistency in implementation practices among teachers. However, the relationship between curriculum implementation and learners' reading performance was found to be weak, suggesting that literacy outcomes are influenced by other factors such as teacher competence, instructional strategies, availability of resources, and institutional support. Based on the findings, the study proposes a teacher-centered action plan focused on continuous professional development through targeted training on differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and reading interventions, along with mentoring, peer collaboration, and regular monitoring. These initiatives aim to strengthen teaching practices and improve learners' reading performance.

Keywords: *Revised K–12 Curriculum, reading performance, curriculum implementation, teacher professional development, elementary education*

INTRODUCTION

Educational systems worldwide continuously undergo reforms to improve learning outcomes, particularly in foundational skills such as reading, which are critical for learners' academic success. Curriculum reforms are central to these efforts, as they shape instructional practices, learning experiences, and assessment approaches within classrooms. Globally, education systems have emphasized streamlined curricula, learner-centered instruction, and competency-based learning to address persistent gaps in literacy and numeracy.

In the Philippines, basic education reforms have been institutionalized through the Republic Act No. 10533, which established the K–12 Basic Education Program to ensure a relevant, responsive, and quality education system. More recently, the Revised K–12 Curriculum, also known as the MATATAG Curriculum, was introduced to address challenges such as congested learning competencies and low learner achievement. The reform focuses on strengthening foundational skills, particularly reading and numeracy, simplifying content, and enhancing instructional delivery to improve overall learner performance.

Despite these policy directions, concerns remain regarding the actual implementation of the revised curriculum at the school level. Teachers play a crucial role in translating curriculum policies into classroom practice; however, variations in teacher preparedness, access to instructional resources, and professional development opportunities may influence the effectiveness of implementation. Empirical studies have highlighted both the potential of the MATATAG Curriculum to improve learning outcomes and the challenges related to training, resource adequacy, and institutional support. While existing research has explored teacher perceptions and curriculum features, there is limited empirical evidence examining how the level of curriculum implementation directly relates to learners' academic performance, particularly in reading.

At the local level, studies focusing on the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum in districts such as Calape, Loon, and Tubigon remain scarce. This gap limits a comprehensive understanding of how curriculum reforms translate into actual classroom practices and whether these practices contribute to improved learner outcomes. Without localized evidence, it becomes difficult for educational leaders to design targeted interventions that address specific implementation challenges and enhance literacy development.

Thus, this study aimed to examine the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum in elementary schools in Calape, Loon, and Tubigon Districts and determine its relationship with learners' reading performance, as measured by the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). The findings of this study provided

empirical evidence that served as a basis for developing an action plan to strengthen curriculum implementation, improve instructional practices, and enhance learners' reading performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum and its relationship to learners' reading performance in elementary schools as a basis for an action plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers in terms of grade level taught, teaching experience, and the number of trainings attended related to the Revised K-12 Curriculum?
2. What is the level of implementation of the Revised K to 12 Curriculum in Calape and Tubigon District in terms of: Curriculum Content and Design; Teaching and Learning Enhancement; and Implementation and Support?
3. What is the level of learners' reading performance based on the latest results of the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA)?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of implementation of the revised K-12 curriculum when teachers are grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the Revised K-12 curriculum and the reading performance of the learners?
6. What action plan can be proposed based on the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum, particularly the MATATAG Curriculum, and its relationship to teachers' perceptions and experiences. The descriptive component was used to describe teachers' views on curriculum content, teaching and learning processes, and implementation support, while the correlational approach determined the relationship between key variables without manipulation. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire measured on a four-point Likert scale to ensure consistency and reliability of responses.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the municipalities of Calape and Tubigon in Bohol, Philippines. Both are coastal areas characterized by a mix of mainland and island barangays, with economies largely dependent on fishing and agriculture. Schools in these districts are distributed across diverse geographic settings, including remote and island communities, which present challenges in accessibility, resource availability, and teacher

support. These conditions make the districts appropriate settings for examining curriculum implementation in varied educational contexts.

Research Participants

The respondents were 141 Grades 1, 2, and 3 elementary teachers from the Calape and Tubigon Districts. Participants were drawn from multiple public elementary schools to represent diverse teaching contexts and experiences. They were selected due to their direct involvement in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum at the foundational level of basic education.

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire adapted from Aquino (2024), which demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.896). The instrument measured three dimensions: curriculum content and design, teaching and learning enhancement, and implementation and support, with each item rated on a four-point Likert scale (4 = Strongly Agree to 1 = Strongly Disagree). Learners' academic performance was measured using records from the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), obtained from teacher advisers with proper consent and confidentiality.

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, necessary approvals were secured from relevant authorities, including the Schools Division Superintendent, Public School District Supervisors, and school principals. Qualified respondents were identified and oriented regarding the purpose of the study, ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality. The questionnaires were then administered, and relevant CRLA data were collected from school records. The gathered data were organized, tabulated, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to determine the level of curriculum implementation and summarize teachers' responses. Inferential statistics were applied to test relationships and differences among variables. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions and experiences in implementing the curriculum. All statistical analyses were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The section presents the data based on the objectives of the study. It includes discussions on the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum, particularly its content, teaching practices, and the support provided in schools. It also examines

teacher-related factors such as grade level handled, teaching experience, and trainings attended.

Furthermore, it discusses learners' reading performance as measured through the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). The information gathered from these variables helps in understanding the key aspects of the study, exploring possible relationships among them, and providing a basis for the development of the proposed action plan.

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the Teachers
n = 141

Variable	Category	f	%
Grade Level Taught	Grade 2	48	34.05
	Grade 3	47	33.33
	Grade 1	46	32.62
Teaching Experience (Years)	21–24	26	18.44
	9–12	24	17.02
	17–20	23	16.31
	13–16	21	14.89
	1–4	21	14.89
	25–28	14	9.93
	5–8	7	4.96
	29–32	4	2.84
	33–36	1	0.71
Number of Trainings Attended	1–2	123	87.23
	3–4	12	8.51
	5–6	4	2.84
	7–8	1	0.71
	15–16	1	0.71
	13–14	0	0.00
	11–12	0	0.00
	9–10	0	0.00
Total		141	100

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the teachers who participated in the study in terms of grade level taught, years of teaching experience, and number of trainings attended related to the Revised K–12 Curriculum.

In terms of grade level taught, the distribution of respondents is nearly equal across Grade 1 (32.62%), Grade 2 (34.05%), and Grade 3 (33.33%), with Grade 2 obtaining the highest frequency. This balanced distribution indicates that the study captured comparable perspectives from teachers handling the foundational stages of learning, which strengthens the validity of comparisons across early grade levels.

For teaching experience, the highest proportion of teachers falls within the 21–24 years category (18.44%), followed by 9–12 years (17.02%) and 17–20 years (16.31%), while the lowest is 33–36 years (0.71%). These findings suggest that the majority of respondents are moderately to highly experienced, indicating a teaching workforce with substantial classroom exposure and familiarity with instructional practices. Such experience is critical in adapting to curriculum reforms, as seasoned teachers are more likely to draw from prior knowledge and pedagogical practices when implementing new curricular changes.

In terms of number of trainings attended, the highest frequency is observed in the 1–2 trainings category (87.23%), while the lowest frequencies are in the 7–8 and 15–16 trainings categories (0.71% each), with no respondents reporting attendance in several higher training brackets. This indicates that although teachers possess extensive teaching experience, their participation in formal and sustained curriculum-related professional development is limited.

Overall, the findings reveal a pattern where strong teaching experience is not matched by equally strong training exposure. This suggests that the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum may rely more on experiential knowledge rather than continuous professional updating. This observation aligns with the work of Shulman (1986), who emphasized that effective teaching requires ongoing integration of content knowledge and pedagogy, which is strengthened through continuous professional development. Similarly, Fullan (2007) argued that successful curriculum reform depends not only on teacher experience but also on sustained professional development and institutional support. These results imply that while teachers are well-distributed across grade levels and possess strong experiential competence, there is a need to strengthen training opportunities to ensure that instructional practices remain aligned with evolving curriculum standards and learner needs.

Table 2
Level of Implementation of the Revised K to 12 Curriculum
n=141

STATEMENTS	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Curriculum Content and Design			
1. The RK-12 Curriculum aligned with the national educational standards.	3.74	0.46	Highly Implemented
2. The learning objectives of the RK-12 Curriculum are cleared and attainable.	3.64	0.55	Highly Implemented
3. The curriculum promoted critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.70	0.51	Highly Implemented
4. The curriculum integrated academic, social, and emotional learning in a balanced manner.	3.71	0.51	Highly Implemented
Composite	3.70	0.51	Highly Implemented
Teaching and Learning Enhancement			
	3.70	0.53	Highly Implemented

1. The teaching methods prescribed by the RK-12 Curriculum enhanced student engagement.			
2. Collaborative learning is effectively facilitated through the curriculum.	3.73	0.49	Highly Implemented
3. The curriculum provided ample opportunities for experiential learning.	3.57	0.56	Highly Implemented
4. The curriculum allowed for flexibility in teaching approaches to cater to different learning styles.	3.59	0.54	Highly Implemented
5. The curriculum employed a systematic approach to evaluating its effectiveness.	3.54	0.60	Highly Implemented
Composite	3.63	0.55	Highly Implemented
Implementation and Support			
1. The curriculum has contributed to students demonstrating increased cultural awareness and appreciation of diversity.	3.59	0.55	Highly Implemented
2. The curriculum employed a systematic approach to evaluating its effectiveness.	3.57	0.58	Highly Implemented
3. The curriculum regularly seeks and utilized student feedback to improved its implementation.	3.52	0.54	Highly Implemented
4. The curriculum recognized teacher feedback as crucial for its continuous improvement.	3.58	0.54	Highly Implemented
Composite	3.56	0.55	Highly Implemented
Overall	3.63	0.54	Highly Implemented

Table 2 presents the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum in terms of curriculum content and design, teaching and learning enhancement, and implementation and support as perceived by the 141 teacher-respondents.

The overall result yielded a composite mean of 3.63 (SD = 0.54), interpreted as Highly Implemented, indicating that the curriculum is generally well applied across the two districts. Among the three domains, Curriculum Content and Design obtained the highest composite mean (M = 3.70), followed by Teaching and Learning Enhancement (M = 3.63), while Implementation and Support registered the lowest composite mean (M = 3.56). This suggests that teachers strongly perceive the curriculum as clear, structured, and aligned with standards, although support mechanisms and evaluation processes are comparatively less emphasized.

At the indicator level, the highest mean was observed in “*The RK–12 Curriculum aligned with the national educational standards*” (M = 3.74), reflecting strong adherence to national policies and curriculum guidelines. This implies that teachers clearly

understand the curriculum framework, which facilitates consistency in instructional delivery. In contrast, the lowest mean was recorded in *“The curriculum regularly seeks and utilizes student feedback to improve its implementation”* (M = 3.52), although still within the “Highly Implemented” range. This indicates that learner feedback, while present, is not maximized as a tool for improving instruction.

These findings imply that while the structural and instructional aspects of the curriculum are effectively implemented, formative evaluation practices and learner participation require further strengthening. The relatively lower emphasis on student feedback suggests that classroom practices may still be more teacher-directed rather than fully learner-centered.

This can be explained through the perspective of Vygotsky (1987), who emphasized that meaningful learning occurs when learners actively engage in the learning process. Limited integration of student feedback may restrict opportunities for interaction, reflection, and adaptive teaching strategies, which are essential in promoting deeper learning.

The findings are consistent with Saro et al. (2024), who reported that teachers tend to rate curriculum implementation highly when it is clearly aligned with standards, supporting the high results in curriculum content and design. Similarly, Aquino (2024) emphasized that effective implementation requires continuous monitoring, evaluation, and institutional support, which aligns with the relatively lower results in implementation and support. Moreover, Inoc et al. (2025) highlighted that responsive teaching practices, including the integration of learner feedback, are essential in improving instructional effectiveness and student engagement. Overall, the results indicate that the Revised K–12 Curriculum is effectively implemented in terms of structure and instructional delivery. However, enhancing evaluation practices, strengthening support systems, and increasing learner participation through feedback mechanisms are necessary to further improve curriculum implementation in the classroom.

Table 3
Level of Learners’ Reading Performance Based on Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) Results
n=141

CRLA Mean Percentage Scores (Average MPS)	Reading Level	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
76 – 100	Grade Level Reader	68	48.23
51– 75	Transitioning Reader	30	21.28
26– 50	Developing Reader	26	18.44
11 – 25	High Emerging Reader	11	7.80

CRLA Mean Percentage Scores (Average MPS)	Reading Level	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
0 – 10	Low Emerging Reader	6	4.25
Total		141	100

Table 3 presents the level of learners' reading performance based on the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) results among 141 learners in Calape and Tubigon Districts.

The data reveal that the highest proportion of learners are classified as Grade Level Readers (48.23%, f = 68), indicating that nearly half of the learners have achieved the expected reading proficiency. This is followed by Transitioning Readers (21.28%) and Developing Readers (18.44%), showing that a considerable number of learners are still progressing toward mastery. On the other hand, the lowest proportions are observed among High Emerging Readers (7.80%) and Low Emerging Readers (4.25%), representing learners who continue to struggle with basic reading skills.

These findings suggest that learners' reading performance is generally at a functional level; however, proficiency is not yet universal. While a significant proportion of learners meet grade-level expectations, the presence of transitioning and developing readers indicates uneven literacy outcomes. This implies that instructional practices may be effective for some learners but may not fully address the needs of those requiring additional support.

This variation in reading performance can be explained through the framework of Lee Shulman, which emphasizes that effective teaching depends on the teacher's ability to transform content into forms that are accessible to diverse learners. The presence of Grade Level Readers reflects the successful application of appropriate teaching strategies, whereas the remaining groups highlight the need for differentiated instruction and targeted interventions to support struggling readers.

The findings are consistent with Nag et al. (2014), who emphasized that strengthening foundational literacy is essential in improving overall learning outcomes. Similarly, Aquino (2025) highlighted the importance of continuous instructional support and monitoring to ensure that learners progress across proficiency levels. Moreover, Bongco and David (2020) underscored the critical role of teachers in shaping learning outcomes, particularly through adaptive teaching practices that respond to learners' varying needs. Overall, while the results indicate that a substantial number of learners have achieved the expected reading level, the presence of learners in lower proficiency categories suggests the need to strengthen instructional approaches. Enhancing differentiated teaching strategies, providing targeted reading interventions, and sustaining instructional support are essential to ensure that all learners attain the desired level of reading proficiency.

Table 4
Difference between the Level of Implementation of the Revised K-12 Curriculum
Based on Grade Level Taught, Teaching Experience, and Number of
Training attended
n=141

Variable	Group	Mean Rank	Test Statistic	α	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Grade Level	Grade 1	67.03	H = 1.95	0.05	.377	Not significant	Do not reject H ₀
	Grade 2	77.48					
	Grade 3	68.27					
Teaching Experience (years)	1–4	59.19	H = 6.02	0.05	.421	Not significant	Do not reject H ₀
	5–8	70.86					
	9–12	67.35					
	13–16	79.48					
	17–20	64.54					
	21–24	83.12					
	25–36	70.58					
Number of Trainings Attended	1–2	70.02	W = 987	0.05	.449	Not significant	Do not reject H ₀
	3 and above	77.67					

Table 4 presents the differences in the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum when teachers are grouped according to grade level taught, teaching experience, and number of trainings attended.

The results show that no significant differences exist in curriculum implementation across all profile variables. For grade level taught, the Kruskal–Wallis test yielded $H = 1.95$, $p = .377$, indicating no significant difference. Although Grade 2 teachers obtained the highest mean rank (77.48) and Grade 1 teachers the lowest (67.03), these variations are minimal and statistically insignificant. This suggests that teachers implement the curriculum in a consistent manner regardless of the grade level they handle.

Similarly, in terms of teaching experience, the results also revealed no significant difference ($H = 6.02$, $p = .421$). While teachers with 21–24 years of experience obtained the highest mean rank (83.12) and those with 1–4 years the lowest (59.19), the differences are not statistically meaningful. This indicates that both novice and

experienced teachers demonstrate comparable levels of curriculum implementation. The finding implies that adherence to standardized curriculum guidelines and shared instructional practices may reduce variability across experience levels.

For the number of trainings attended, the Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test also showed no significant difference ($W = 987, p = .449$). Teachers who attended three or more trainings had a higher mean rank (77.67) compared to those who attended 1–2 trainings (70.02); however, this difference remains statistically insignificant. This suggests that the number of trainings alone does not necessarily translate to improved curriculum implementation, highlighting that the quality, relevance, and application of training may be more critical than frequency.

Overall, the findings indicate that the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum is uniform across teacher groups, regardless of grade level, years of experience, or training exposure. This consistency suggests that curriculum implementation is guided more by standardized policies, institutional practices, and shared expectations rather than individual teacher characteristics.

These results are supported by Durlak and DuPre (2008), who found that implementation practices are largely influenced by systemic conditions such as resource availability and institutional support rather than individual teacher differences. Similarly, Kumayas et al. (2025) emphasized that teachers’ experiences in implementing curriculum reforms are shaped by contextual and organizational realities within the education system. Gouëdard et al. (2020) further highlighted that effective curriculum implementation depends on system-level support mechanisms, including collaboration, mentoring, and continuous professional development. In summary, the absence of significant differences across teacher profiles reinforces the view that successful curriculum implementation is primarily a function of institutional and systemic support rather than individual demographic factors.

Table 5
Relationship between the Level of Implementation of the Revised K-12 Curriculum and Teachers’ Profile
n=141

Variables	ρ	Description	α	p -value	Interpretation	Decision
Implementation of Revised K-12 Curriculum and Reading Performance of Learners	.11	Positive, weak	.05	.194	Not significant	Do not reject H_0

Table 5 presents the relationship between the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum and learners’ reading performance as measured through the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA).

The results reveal a weak positive correlation ($\rho = .11$) between curriculum implementation and reading performance; however, this relationship is not statistically significant ($p = .194 > .05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates that although better implementation is slightly associated with higher reading performance, the relationship is too weak to establish a meaningful or reliable connection.

This finding suggests that effective implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum alone does not necessarily lead to significant improvements in learners' reading performance. While the curriculum may be properly delivered, other factors likely play a more influential role in shaping literacy outcomes. These may include learner motivation, home support, teacher instructional strategies, availability of learning resources, and school-level interventions.

From a theoretical perspective, this result can be explained by Systems Theory (von Bertalanffy, 1968), which posits that educational outcomes are influenced by multiple interconnected components within a system. In this context, curriculum implementation is only one element among many, and improvements in reading performance require the alignment of several factors, including teacher competence, instructional quality, and institutional support.

The findings are supported by Soriano (2025), who emphasized that while the MATATAG Curriculum prioritizes foundational literacy, its effectiveness depends heavily on teacher training and the availability of adequate instructional support. Similarly, Johnson (2006) identified resource constraints and limited professional development as barriers that may weaken the impact of curriculum implementation on learner outcomes. Furthermore, Stoll et al. (2002) argued that educational change is a complex process that requires sustained support systems, collaboration, and capacity-building efforts beyond policy implementation. Overall, the results indicate that improving learners' reading performance requires a more comprehensive and integrated approach. While curriculum implementation remains essential, it must be complemented by strengthened teacher development programs, adequate learning resources, and targeted instructional interventions to effectively enhance literacy outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This study focused on examining the implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum, particularly the MATATAG Curriculum, and its relationship to learners' reading performance in the districts of Calape and Tubigon. It specifically investigated how teachers implement the curriculum in terms of content and design, teaching and learning practices, and implementation and support. The study also considered teacher-related factors such as grade level taught, teaching experience, and number of trainings attended to determine whether these variables influence the level of curriculum implementation. In addition, it assessed learners' reading performance using the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) to determine their level of reading proficiency. Furthermore, the study examined whether there are significant differences in

curriculum implementation when teachers are grouped according to their profile and whether there is a relationship between curriculum implementation and learners' reading performance. The findings of the study served as the basis for developing an action plan aimed at improving curriculum implementation and enhancing learners' reading outcomes.

Findings

The findings of the study are as follows:

1. Teachers were almost equally distributed across Grade 1, Grade 2, and Grade 3, indicating balanced representation among early-grade teachers. In terms of teaching experience, the majority of respondents had moderate to extensive years in service, particularly within the 21–24 years range. However, most teachers reported attending only 1–2 trainings related to the Revised K–12 Curriculum, suggesting limited exposure to sustained professional development despite their considerable teaching experience.
2. The level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum was found to be highly implemented across all domains, namely Curriculum Content and Design, Teaching and Learning Enhancement, and Implementation and Support. This indicates that teachers generally adhere to curriculum standards, apply appropriate instructional strategies, and demonstrate effective delivery of learning competencies in the classroom.
3. Learners' reading performance, as measured using the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), was generally high. A significant proportion of learners were classified as Grade Level Readers, although a considerable number remained at transitioning and developing levels, indicating that not all learners have fully achieved the expected reading proficiency.
4. There was no significant difference in the level of curriculum implementation when teachers were grouped according to grade level taught, years of teaching experience, and number of trainings attended. This suggests that curriculum implementation is consistent across different teacher profiles and is not significantly influenced by these demographic variables.
5. The relationship between the level of implementation of the Revised K–12 Curriculum and learners' reading performance was found to be weak positive but not statistically significant. This indicates that while there is a slight association between the two variables, curriculum implementation alone does not significantly influence learners' reading outcomes.
6. Based on the findings, an action plan was proposed focusing on enhancing teacher training, strengthening instructional support systems, and implementing targeted reading interventions. These strategies aim to improve

curriculum implementation and address gaps in learners' reading performance, particularly among those who have not yet reached the expected proficiency level.

Conclusions

The study concludes that teachers in Calape and Tubigon generally perceive the Revised K–12 Curriculum positively, particularly in its clarity, alignment with standards, and ability to support student engagement. While many learners demonstrate satisfactory reading performance based on the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), some still struggle, indicating gaps in literacy achievement. The findings further show that teacher profile variables do not significantly affect curriculum implementation, and that the relationship between implementation and reading performance is weak and not significant. This suggests that curriculum implementation alone is not enough to improve reading outcomes. Overall, improving learners' reading performance requires stronger teacher support, continuous training, and targeted instructional strategies to address diverse learner needs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The School Head/Principal, in coordination with the District Supervisor, may conduct a Differentiated Instruction Strategies Workshop to help teachers address diverse learner needs, particularly those who are struggling in reading.
2. The District Supervisor, together with Master Teachers, may organize a Collaborative and Experiential Learning Workshop to enhance teachers' use of interactive and learner-centered teaching strategies.
3. The Reading Coordinator and English/Filipino Subject Coordinators may facilitate a Reading Intervention and Literacy Support Workshop to equip teachers with effective approaches for improving learners' reading performance.
4. The School Head/Principal may initiate mentorship and peer-sharing sessions to allow experienced teachers to support and guide their colleagues in strengthening instructional practices.
5. The School Administration, in coordination with the Division Office, may enhance the provision of instructional materials and learning resources to support effective curriculum implementation across grade levels.
6. The School Head/Principal, together with the District Supervisor and Master Teachers, may implement the proposed action plan with regular monitoring and feedback mechanisms to ensure continuous improvement in teaching practices and learners' reading outcomes.

7. Future researchers may explore other factors influencing learners' reading performance, such as home environment, learner motivation, and access to resources, and may consider broader samples or alternative research designs to further validate and extend the findings of this study.

Proposed Action Plan

Strengthening Teacher Competency and Learner Reading Outcomes through Differentiated, Collaborative, and Data-Informed Instruction

Rationale

The findings of the study revealed that although teachers demonstrate a generally positive perception of curriculum implementation and most learners exhibit satisfactory reading performance, the relationship between curriculum practices and reading outcomes remains weak. This suggests inconsistencies in instructional delivery and highlights the need to enhance teacher competencies, particularly in differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and data-informed teaching. Furthermore, limited participation in sustained professional development and the presence of learners requiring additional reading support indicate gaps in instructional responsiveness. These findings underscore the need for a structured intervention that focuses on continuous teacher development and targeted instructional improvement. Thus, this proposed action plan is designed to strengthen teachers' competencies and improve learner reading outcomes through job-embedded professional learning, mentoring, and collaborative practices.

Objectives

To enhance teacher competency and improve learner reading outcomes through differentiated, collaborative, and data-informed instructional practices.

Specific Objectives

1. Strengthen teachers' knowledge of differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and reading intervention strategies;
2. Develop teachers' skills in designing and implementing learner-centered and inclusive lesson plans;
3. Enhance teachers' ability to analyze learner data and adjust instruction accordingly;
4. Promote collaborative and reflective teaching practices through CE/LAC sessions and mentoring; and
5. Improve reading performance of learners through targeted instructional interventions.

Description of the Intervention

The intervention is a six-month job-embedded professional development program that integrates workshops, mentoring, and collaborative learning activities. It focuses on improving instructional practices and strengthening teachers' capacity to address diverse learner needs.

The program includes three major components:

1. **Differentiated Instruction Training** – equips teachers with strategies to design responsive and inclusive lessons;
2. **Collaborative and Experiential Learning Training** – enhances student engagement through interactive and group-based approaches;
3. **Reading Intervention Training** – provides teachers with tools to identify struggling readers and apply appropriate interventions.

The implementation is supported through CE/LAC sessions, peer mentoring, classroom observations, and reflective practices to ensure continuous improvement.

Implementation Plan

Phase	Key Activities	Timeline	Expected Output
Phase 1: Capacity Building	Conduct workshops on differentiated instruction	Month 1	Lesson plans addressing diverse learners
Phase 2: Instructional Enhancement	Conduct collaborative and experiential learning workshops	Months 2–3	Improved classroom engagement strategies
Phase 3: Reading Intervention	Conduct reading intervention training	Months 3–4	Intervention plans for struggling readers
Phase 4: Implementation & Monitoring	Apply strategies, conduct mentoring and observations	Months 4–5	Improved instructional practices
Phase 5: Evaluation & Reporting	Consolidate results and prepare reports	Month 6	Program evaluation and action plans

Monitoring and Evaluation

The effectiveness of the intervention will be evaluated through:

- Review of lesson plans and instructional materials;
- Classroom observations and mentoring reports;
- Analysis of learner reading performance data; and
- Documentation of CE/LAC sessions and reflective outputs.

Expected Outcomes

1. Improved teacher competency in differentiated and data-informed instruction;
2. Increased collaboration and reflective teaching practices;
3. Enhanced classroom engagement and instructional effectiveness; and
4. Improved learner reading performance, particularly among struggling readers.

The proposed intervention directly addresses the gaps identified in the study by strengthening teacher competencies and aligning instructional practices with learner needs. Through continuous professional development and collaborative support, the program is expected to contribute to improved reading outcomes and overall instructional quality.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of research. Participation of the respondents was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was secured after clearly explaining the purpose of the study, procedures involved, and their rights, including the option to withdraw at any stage without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and no personally identifiable information was collected from the participants. All data were treated with utmost confidentiality, securely stored, and used solely for academic and research purposes. The study complied with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure proper handling and protection of personal data. Furthermore, the study posed no physical, psychological, or social risk to the participants. No form of incentive or compensation was provided, ensuring that participation remained free from coercion or undue influence.

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